

Damascus Document

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Entry tags: Late Second Temple Judaism, Jewish Traditions, Religious Group, Text, Abrahamic, Early Jewish Literature, Messianism, Communal Society, Rule Text

The Damascus Document is a rule text of the Judean religious group associated with the Dead Sea Scrolls (a group commonly, though debatably, identified as Essene). It first came to light in the early 20th century when Solomon Schechter published two medieval manuscripts (10th and 12th c. CE) from the genizah (manuscript storeroom) of a synagogue in Cairo. After fragments of ten more manuscripts of the same work were discovered among the Dead Sea Scrolls from Khirbet Qumran, it became obvious that the document had originated among the members of that movement. Since the oldest copies from Qumran (4Q267 and 4Q266) date to the late 2nd and early 1st centuries BCE, it seems likely that the document was composed or redacted in the mid-2nd century by the larger sectarian group (possibly the Essenes) and was then brought to Qumran by the particular expression of the group that lived there. In consequence, the text displays a trajectory of editing from more universally applicable to more overtly sectarian. In terms of content, the text mainly contains religious laws, based in part on interpretations of the Jewish Torah, intended to guide the life and practice of the group's adherents. These laws are comprised of two strata—one that presents a legal vision for the nation of Israel as a whole and one that specifically regulates the practice of the sectarian community. Across these strata, the laws deal with a wide variety of matters including, inter alia, marriage and sex, ritual purity, oaths and vows, Sabbath observance, food taboos, theft, interaction with Gentiles, and communal organization. The document also frames these laws with significant portions of text devoted to justifying the legitimacy of the laws and exhorting the sect's current members to live by them. According to the text, the laws were divinely revealed to the sect's founders several centuries after the Babylonian invasion of Judah (early 6th c. BCE) through the instrumentality of a founding teacher. The text presents the laws as true interpretations of the Torah of Moses and encourages members of the movement to take an oath of return to this Torah. As adherents to these laws, the text styles the community's members as a unique group of faithful ones who hold fast to God's covenant during the "Epoch of Wickedness," a temporary period characterized by societal corruption under the influence of a supernatural figure known as Belial. The text contains promises of reward to those who persevere in the way of life presented in the laws as well as warnings of destruction for those who depart from it. The Damascus Document thus provides an important window into the history of the Dead Sea Scrolls sectarian community, the community's vision of religious law, and its members' understanding of their own epoch in light of the eschaton.

Date Range: 200 BCE - 50 CE

Region: Judea and Cairo

Region tags: Israel, Egypt, Palestine, Cairo, Judah, Qumran

Locations of the discovery of the manuscripts

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hempel, Charlotte. *The Damascus Texts. Companion to the Qumran Scrolls 1*; Sheffield Academic Press, 2000.
- Source 2: Baumgarten, Joseph M. *Qumran Cave 4. XIII. The Damascus Document (4Q266-273)*. DJD 18; Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1996.
- Source 3: Broshi, Magen, ed. *The Damascus Document Reconsidered*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society and Shrine of the Book, 1992

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 1200 CE

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/manuscript/4Q266-1?locale=en_US
- Source 1 Description: Photos of the Qumran Cave 4 Manuscripts
- Source 2 URL: <https://cudl.lib.cam.ac.uk/view/MS-TS-00010-K-00006/1>
- Source 2 Description: Photos of the Cairo Genizah Manuscripts

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 1200 CE

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Papyrus

Notes: One of the Cave 4 manuscripts (4Q273) is comprised of papyrus fragments.

- Paper

Notes: The Cairo Genizah manuscripts are paper.

- Other textile: Leather

Notes: The Cave 5 (5Q12) and Cave 6 (6Q15) manuscripts are leather.

- Other textile: Parchment

Notes: All except one of the Cave 4 manuscripts is parchment.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Many of the Qumran manuscripts have vertical and horizontal ruled lines.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery
– No

↳ Temple
– No

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– Yes

Notes: Later copies were found in the genizah (manuscript repository) of the Ben Ezra Synagogue in Cairo.

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: Fragments were found in caves 4, 5, and 6 at Qumran.

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that the production was funded by contributions from the members of the Dead Sea Scrolls sect ("polity" in that narrow sense), but this is unconfirmed.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The question of scripture at Qumran is complex. The Dead Sea Scrolls community considered a variety of texts to be sacred and authoritative, texts beyond those that would make up the later Jewish canon. The Damascus Document itself claims to preserve divinely sanctioned religious laws (interpretations and applications of the Torah of Moses) that it calls "the Torah for the Epoch of Wickedness" (CD 4:14). In this sense, it claims significant authority for itself as an expression of God's will. However, it is difficult to say (and perhaps unlikely) that it rose to the same status as central "scriptural" texts such as the book of the Torah or the classical prophets.

Reference: Molly Zahn. "Torah for 'The Age of Wickedness': The Authority of the Damascus and Serekh Texts in Light of Biblical and Rewritten Traditions."

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

Notes: The Damascus Document is written in a Hebrew that was likely similar to the Hebrew used by the majority of Jewish scribes in the late Second Temple Period. But the language is at the same time pervaded by features that reflect religious ideology and the distinctive identity of the sect. These features include archaizing language, unusually orthography, and "insider" vocabulary.

Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– I don't know

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: The text mentions those who join the sectarian movement and outlines guidelines for their initiation and participation in the community. It also describes negative consequences for those who refuse to join. It does not, however, explicitly encourage proselytizing. Note also that their focus was on drawing fellow Jews into a reform movement, though Gentiles were probably also welcome (cf. CD 14:6).

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Qumran fragments overlap with each other in a number of places. In these cases, the amount of divergence is relatively minimal. The Cairo Genizah manuscripts, however, lack material present in the Qumran texts. Does this point to the existence of an early, shorter version, or does it point instead to accidental loss in transmission? Given the relative consistency of the Qumran manuscripts, the latter option is more likely. Still, the situation is further complicated by the fact that the two Cairo Genizah manuscripts (A and B) present a portion of the text that is both very similar and yet diverges significantly in one chunk of text (CD 7:9-8:2 vs 19:5-14). This is vexing problem to which no solution has yet been agreed upon by scholars.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the sense that it was preserved in caves along with a large number of other texts.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– I don't know

Notes: This depends on the definition of important literary tradition. It does link with a constellation of texts produced by the Dead Sea Scrolls movement that can be called rule texts, which specifically outline expectations for participation in the community. The most important of these are the Community Rule, or Serekh, texts.

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The laws seem to consist of two strata: (1) one outlining a legal vision for the people of Israel at large and (2) one outlining a legal vision for the specific manifestations of organized sectarian community (called "camps").

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The texts indicates a structure within the community by which issues concerning the religious law contained in the document were evaluated and decided. At the center of this structure was a figure called the mebaqqer ("inspector") whose duties apparently included overseeing the initiation of new members, instructing members in the law, hearing disputes or accusations, consulting about marriages and financial transactions, and generally caring for the welfare of the community. Alongside this figure were priests who were particularly responsible for evaluating matters of purity and impurity, and "judges" who heard and decided cases and dispersed resources in the community.

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– No

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– Yes

↳ Exile?

– No

↳ Corporal punishments?

– No

↳ Ostracism?

– Yes

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, if this includes the paying of fines and/or restitution of damaged or stolen property.

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The Dead Sea Scrolls community was interested in calendrical matters and multiple texts from the movement attest to a 364-day calendar. But calendar does not play a significant role in the Damascus Document, though at least one passage may imply a polemic against those in mainstream Judaism who celebrated festivals on the incorrect dates (CD 3:13-15).

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are several references to an individual's spirit (CD 3:3, 3:7, 5:11, 20:24), but the precise meaning of this and the relationship of this aspect of the person to that person's body is not clear.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is only slight indication: those who "hold firm" are promised "eternal life" (3:20).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– Yes

Notes: Again, the one reference to "eternal life" (CD 3:20).

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: The only possible connection is a statement that any instrument, nail, or peg that is in the wall of a house where a corpse lies shall be considered unclean (CD 12:17-18).

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: Anthropomorphic descriptions of God may be occasionally present, but are not a distinctive feature of the text.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: He is described as knowing and interacting with human affairs. He is particularly ascribed knowledge of the unfolding of the future. "He knows the times of appearance and the number and exact times of everything that has ever existed and ever will exist before it happens in the proper time, for all the years of eternity" (CD 2:9-10).

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - I don't know
 - Notes: This depends on whether the knowledge of character is based upon concrete manifestations of character or is known apart from these. In the text, God is said to consider the deeds of certain people as a means of knowing their heart. "But God considered their deeds, that they had sought Him with a whole heart" (CD 1:10).
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– I don't know

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes
Notes: Said to become angry (CD 3:12).

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Can be tricked?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

Notes: The text deploys many quotations from ancient prophetic and legal texts as support for or explication of its statements. These quotations assume a belief in divine communication through human intermediaries, though the way in which this communication occurred--and the state of the intermediary--is not explained in detail. The text furthermore presents itself as a compendium of laws that have been arrived at by means of a kind of revelatory interaction with these ancient texts. A word that is used to describe this interaction is the verb "darash," which in other texts can be used to describe divination.

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams
– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Three supernatural beings, aside from the supreme God, appear in the text. These are the "watchers of heaven," Belial, and the Angel of Mastemah. The watchers of heaven are beings who, in the enochic tradition, cohabitated with human women and disseminated various kinds of knowledge to humans. The Damascus Document mentions the fall of these watchers and their offspring (CD 2:18-19). Belial seems to be a being who is fundamentally characterized by enmity with God. He is given a time to run unrestrained in Israel (CD 4:13), during which time he ensnares people in three traps: "fornication," "wealth," and "defiling the sanctuary" (CD 4:17-18). The Angel of Mastemah ("hostility") is mentioned once in reference to what happens to a person who takes an oath to return to the Torah of Moses. It is said that "the Angel of Mastemah will leave him" (CD 16:5).

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– Yes

Notes: Belial is identified as an agent of divine punishment. Those who do not hold fast to the laws outlined in the document are "punished so as to be destroyed by Belial" (CD 19:14).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Field doesn't know

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, insofar as the offspring of the watchers and human women are divine-human. According to the text, they were "as tall as cedars" and their "bodies were as big as mountains" (CD 2:19).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Field doesn't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: These answers have to do with the community's concept of the supreme God.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– I don't know

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: There is an assumption in a few passages of participation in sacrifice at the altar in the Jewish temple in Jerusalem, but this does not play a significant role in the document and the relationship to supernatural monitoring is not thoroughly described.

↳ Libations?

– I don't know

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

Notes: The Temple

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– Field doesn't know

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Also prohibited is having sex with a menstruating woman and taking two wives during one's lifetime (CD 4:20-5:7). Also taking as a wife a woman with a questionable sexual past.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: There is concern with the status and trustworthiness of witnesses in cases of accusation. Cf. CD 9:16-10:3. There is also a consequence for one who lies in financial matters (CD 14:20).

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: Prohibition against necromancers and soothsayers (4QDe 2 i 9-ii 18; 6QD 5.1-5).

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: There is a prohibition against murmuring against fathers or mothers.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: This would include ritual washing and Sabbath observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: Each member of the community is expected to contribute two days' wages each month which would then be distributed to the poor, elderly, sick, and those without family support (CD 14:13-16).

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: There is a concern with purity that leads to regulations concerning matters such as child-birth and skin disease.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: For those that reject the way of life that the community believes that God has prescribed, God will bring punishment. This punishment is often described as "destruction" (e.g. CD 8:2), which in at

least one place is further described as being handed over to the sword on the day of the Messiah's appearance (CD 19:12). A further, or related, punishment is exclusion from the people of God when eschatological events unfold (CD 20:26). It seems that God uses agents for this punishment that include "angels of destruction" (CD 2:6) and Belial (8:2).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that there is not always a clear distinction between direct causation by God and causation by a person's actions.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– I don't know

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

Notes: This distinction between lifetime and afterlife is a difficult one for this text since the perspective seems to be mainly that an individual should expect destruction or annihilation during an imminent eschatological period.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Rewards for persevering adherence to God's way of life include happiness, atonement for sin/impurity, God's deliverance, and, it seems, eternal life (CD 3:20). One of the most complete descriptions of these rewards is CD 20:27-34: "But all who hold fast to these rules, going out and coming in according to the Law, always obeying the Teacher and confessing to God as follows: 'We have wickedly sinned, we and our ancestors by living contrary to the covenant laws; just and true are Your judgments against us' and do not act arrogantly against His holy laws and His righteous ordinances and His reliable declarations and who discipline themselves by the ancient laws by which the members of the Yahad were governed and listen attentively to the Teacher of Righteousness, not abandoning the correct laws when they hear them: they will rejoice and be happy and exultant. They will prevail over all the inhabitants of the earth. Then God will make atonement for them and they will experience His deliverance because they have trusted in His holy name."

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– I don't know

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Damascus Document contains several references to a messiah or messiahs (CD 12:23-13:1, 14:19, 19:10-11, 19:35-20:1). The usual reference is to "the messiah of Aaron and Israel," which presumably either indicates a single messianic figure who is characterized by both priestly and royal descent or two messiahs, one of priestly lineage and one of royal lineage. The exact timing of the coming of the messiah(s) is not specified in the text nor is the precise role that he/they will play. The coming of the messiah(s) serves in the text primarily as a temporal marker of a turning point in history, an eschatological transition.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– No

Notes: There are two possible indications of the purpose or role of the messiah(s), but little beyond these. The first is a reference to the "scepter" from Numbers 24:17 who is interpreted to be the "prince of the whole nation" who will destroy "all the sons of Seth" (CD 7:19-21). The second is a reference to "the one who teaches righteousness at the end of days" (CD 6:11). The identity of these figures is, however, debated.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

- ↳ At specified time in future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - Yes
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - No
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: The extent of restoration is not clear.
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive
 - Yes

- ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton
- No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
- Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
- Yes

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
- Yes

- ↳ Cooperation
- Yes

- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
- Yes

- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
- Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Incest

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: Incest

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: The text prohibits eating blood and other foods barred by the Torah of Moses, including (the text specifies) larvae of bees, living things that creep in the water, fish that has not been cut open and emptied of blood while alive, locusts not dipped in water or passed through fire while alive. See CD 12:11-15.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The main ritual described in the text is a ceremony for expulsion of members and a gathering of all members to curse the one who turns away from the way of the community (see 4QDa 11; 4QDc 7 i-ii).

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– Yes

Notes: This is assumed from CD 12:11 and prevalent Jewish practice in the Second Temple period.

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Notes: On a few occasions, a fellow Jew or community member is referred to as a "brother" (e.g. CD 6:20-7:1).

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: The text, in a few places, regulates sacrifices to be given at the altar of the Jerusalem temple. These regulations likely form part of a stratum of the laws that presents a legal vision for the nation of Israel as a whole and therefore assumes temple worship. The text does not directly prescribe sacrifices or describe them in detail.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Each member of the community is expected to contribute two days' wages each month which would then be distributed to the poor, elderly, sick, and those without family support (CD 14:13-16).

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: CD 14:13-16 seems to indicate this, depending on how the relevant term is reconstructed and translated.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The exact contexts for use and study of the Damascus Document are unknown.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in broad sense. The Mebaqqer is given the responsibility of teaching the Torah to the community. New initiates are to learn and be examined. Knowledge of the Torah and something called the Book of Hagi are highly valued.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: CD 15:5-15 requires the children of community members to be made to take an oath to return to the Torah of Moses and to be examined for initiation concerning their knowledge of the laws. It is not clear whether the term for "children" in this passage limits to male or also includes female children.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Full participation in the community (cf. CD 15:15).

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: There is no comprehensive system of bureaucracy given in the text, but several leadership roles are mentioned which are given somewhat defined boundaries (see the section on legal codes above). As a pertinent example, it is always the priest's responsibility to render a decision on matters of skin disease (CD 13:6).

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, members are required to give two days' wages per month for the relief of the poor and vulnerable.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions brief regulations on agriculture and the slaughter and consumption of animals.

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

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